

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

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EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
EPIC-WE	Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments
TH	Triple Helix
QH	Quadruple Helix
DBR	Design-Based Research and Innovation
LL	Living Lab
CLL	Cultural Living Lab
HEI	Higher Education Institution
CI	Creative Industry
CHI	Cultural Heritage Institution
YC	Youth Citizens
YAB	Youth Advisory Board
QH Cultural Hub	Quadruple Helix Cultural Hub
CGJ	Cultural Game Jam
EPIC-WE CGJ	EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam
AUAS	Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences
DM	Dropstoff Media
NISV	Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision
UL	Lusófona University
BS	Battleship
CMO	Obidós Municipal Council
AU	Aarhus University
AAKS	Filmby Aarhus
ARoS	ARoS Aarhus Kunstmuseum

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START

Summary of Deliverable

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

Summary of Deliverable

This report presents the outcomes of Work Package 4 (WP4) of the EPIC-WE project: *Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments (2023–2026)*, which explores how cultural heritage institutions (CHIs), creative industries (CIs), higher education institutions (HEIs), and youth can collaborate through Cultural Game Jams (CGJs) to reimagine culture and foster empowered participation. EPIC-WE operationalises this through a developed and tested Quadruple Helix (QH) Cultural Innovation Ecosystem, carried out in Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs (QH Cultural Hubs) that function as real-world living labs for participatory cultural innovation.

Across three European sites – Aarhus (Denmark), Hilversum (the Netherlands), and Óbidos (Portugal) – twelve Cultural Game Jams (CGJs) were conducted by the QH Cultural Hubs as iterative Design-Based Research interventions. Participants explored European values, heritage, and identity through game-making, combining creativity, research, and co-creation. Cultural Hubs provided tangible and virtual spaces, reconfiguring museums, heritage sites, and public areas into shared, participatory environments that emphasized space, rhythm, and context in cultural engagement.

By developing, implementing, and testing these twelve CGJs across the three European QH Cultural Hubs, the project explored how the QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem functions in practice, evolving and implementing principles for cross-sector, participatory cultural innovation. This report examines the six principles developed in WP3 ([D3.1, Protocol 1](#) and [D3.2, Protocol 1](#) on Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation; [D3.3: Report on Insights from the Design and Construction of Ecosystems and Game Jams](#)) that guided the QH Cultural Hubs: democratizing cultural innovation, forming equal and transformative partnerships, meeting in the middle, co-creating for public good(s), developing real-world Cultural Hubs, and advancing empowered participation. These principles structured reflection on how diverse partners interact, share responsibility, and contribute to co-creation. Youth participation was central, with the introduction of Youth Advisory Boards (YABs) ensuring genuine agency, co-ownership, and influence in Cultural Game Jam design, facilitation, and dissemination.

Reflections highlight both successes and challenges in applying the QH Ecosystem and Cultural Hub model. QH Cultural Hubs demonstrated that real-world spaces, iterative facilitation, and flexible approaches foster meaningful engagement, while balancing capacities, expectations, and communication across sectors required ongoing negotiation. The report shows how game-making can serve as a medium for cultural dialogue, co-creation, and youth empowerment within a QH Ecosystem.

Ultimately, this reflective analysis shows that the QH Ecosystem and Cultural Hub model is not a fixed framework but a dynamic, adaptive approach. When implemented thoughtfully, it

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

enables collaborative innovation, transformative partnerships, and participatory cultural practice, providing lessons for future cross-sector projects in Europe and beyond.

Table of Contents

Introduction	8
Principle 1: Democratize cultural innovation by including citizens and users as core partners in the QH Cultural Hub	14
Explanation	14
Experience	14
Reflection	17
Conclusion	19
Principle 2: Form equal and transformative partnerships in cultural innovation	20
Explanation	20
Experience	20
Reflection	21
Conclusion	24
Principle 3: Institute meetings in the middle	26
Explanation	26
Experience	27
Reflection	27
Conclusion	29
Principle 4: Practice co-creative cultural innovation and transformation for public good(s)	30
Explanation	30
Experience	31
Reflection	32
Conclusion	32
Principle 5: Develop real-world, real-life QH Cultural Hub	33
Explanation	33
Experience	33
Reflection	37
Conclusion	39
Principle 6: Advance Empowered Participation in Culture	41
Explanation	41
Experience	41
Reflection	43
Conclusion	46
Final conclusion	47

Introduction

Introduction

EPIC-WE (Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments) is a Horizon Europe-funded project running from 2023 to 2026. The project aims to empower youth citizens (YCs) to actively participate in shaping European culture and their own futures by ‘imagining, creating and exchanging cultural values and heritage through game-making’. At its core, EPIC-WE explores innovative systems, models, and activities for cultural collaboration, knowledge exchange, and empowered participation, providing practical frameworks for co-creation between diverse societal actors.

To realise these ambitions, EPIC-WE develops and iteratively tests Cultural Game Jams (CGJs): immersive, hands-on events where game-making is engaged as culture-making and simultaneously as a medium through which culture is experienced and interpreted. Across three European sites – Óbidos (Portugal), Hilversum (the Netherlands), and Aarhus (Denmark) – the project implemented twelve interventions in the form of CGJs. These serve as both experimental living labs and practical demonstrations of the broader EPIC-WE cultural innovation model and ecosystem.

The backbone of the project on which this report will reflect is the EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem (QH), which brings together higher education institutions (HEIs), cultural heritage institutions (CHIs), creative industries (CIs), and youth citizens (YCs) as active partners. This report builds on the WP3 reports [D3.1](#) and [D3.2](#) reports on Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation and the research knowledge/publications developed in the project. Together with EPIC-WE Cultural Hubs (CHs) and CGJs, the QH Ecosystem provides a transferable and scalable framework that operationalises collaboration, co-creation, and cultural innovation. By bringing together each of these four societal domains in three Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs (QH Cultural Hubs), the project fosters transformative cross-sector partnerships in which each partner contributes unique knowledge, methods, and perspectives: HEIs contribute research, education, and culturally sensitive frameworks; CHIs provide heritage, spaces, and expertise; CIs offer game-making tools, practices, and design knowledge; and YCs bring creativity, lived experience, and cultural insight into the process.

In practice, the EPIC-WE consortium itself functions as a living Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem. Each partner type represents a distinct societal domain, and the QH Cultural Hubs bringing the partners together operate on the principle of ‘meeting in the middle’, where these diverse knowledges and practices converge to form equitable and interwoven partnerships. This approach enables new forms of cultural dialogue, co-creation, and participation, supporting both the personal empowerment of youth citizens and the development of shared cultural products such as games that are meaningful, culturally sensitive, and reflective of European heritage and values.

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

The project operates as a Design-Based Research (DBR) and Innovation initiative, in which theory, design practice, and iterative empirical testing are closely intertwined. The macro-level framework (the EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem) defines the roles and relationships between sectors and partners; the meso-level (EPIC-WE QH Cultural Hub model) structures collaboration within local-glocal hubs; and the micro-level (EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jams) provides concrete, experimental events and sites for testing QH Cultural Hub co-creation methodologies and evaluating outcomes. Taken together, these layers allow EPIC-WE to systematically develop, examine and advance models of cultural co-creation and innovation while maintaining active youth participation as a central pillar of the process.

Theoretical Background

From Triple to Quadruple Helix

Traditional innovation models, such as the Triple Helix (TH) model, emphasise collaboration between academia, industry, and government and suggest that in a knowledge-based society, the distinctions between these sectors are becoming increasingly blurred (Leydesdorff and Etzkowitz, 1995). These models focus on trilateral relationships to generate technological, economic, and organisational innovation within their respective sectors. However, in cultural and creative sectors, this approach is often insufficient. Innovation is not solely technical; it is social, cultural, and participatory, requiring active engagement with the public and the communities for whom the innovations are created.

The Quadruple Helix (QH) framework extends the TH model by introducing the fourth helix: the public, specifically conceived as the culture- and media-based public and civil society (D3.2, Protocol 1, Nørgård and Holflod, 2025). This inclusion positions citizens as active participants in research and innovation, rather than end-users or passive consumers of outputs. By embedding societal perspectives into the innovation process, the QH model emphasises collective knowledge production, co-creation, and cultural relevance. It is therefore particularly suited to projects like EPIC-WE, where youth engagement, cultural imagination, and participatory innovation are central.

The EPIC-WE project chose to use the Quadruple Helix ecosystem model, because we believed in the added value of nurturing complexity and difference, exploring together, and finding synergies and opportunities in the spaces between our different social worlds. In the context of cultural innovation, the QH model serves as a driver of social and cultural change. It foregrounds the production, dissemination, and valorisation of knowledge through collaborative and participatory practices, ensuring that innovations respond to real societal and cultural needs. In EPIC-WE, this translates into youth citizens shaping game-based cultural interventions alongside CHIs, CIs, and HEIs, reflecting a broader societal purpose and reinforcing the civic and cultural roles of all partners.

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

Why the QH is necessary for cultural and creative sectors

Cultural innovation differs fundamentally from technological innovation. It involves cultural values, narratives, participation, identity, and community engagement, which cannot be adequately addressed without integrating societal actors directly into the innovation process. Using the knowledge and principles created in WP3, about which the reader can learn more in [D3.1, Protocol 1: Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation](#), [D3.2, Protocol 1: Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation](#) and [D3.3: Report on Insights from the Design and Constructions of Ecosystems and Game Jams](#), the QH framework supports:

- User- and citizen-centred approaches, ensuring that innovations are socially relevant and culturally meaningful.
- Collective creation and participatory knowledge production, fostering shared ownership and sustainability.
- Integration of diverse perspectives, enabling co-creation across local, national, and European contexts.

In EPIC-WE, the inclusion of youth as the fourth helix ensures that cultural co-creation is democratically grounded, contextually relevant, and transformative, while simultaneously offering opportunities for youth empowerment and skill development.

Living Labs as a methodological operationalisation

While the QH provides a conceptual framework for multi-stakeholder collaboration, Living Labs (LLs) operationalise these principles in practice. LLs are real-world environments in which innovation is co-created, tested, and refined with end-users and stakeholders. As outlined in [D3.1, Protocol 1: Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation](#), LLs emphasise:

- Participation and co-creation with end-users, treating them as equal partners;
- Experiments in authentic environments, rather than isolated test sites;
- Iterative and multidisciplinary approaches, including workshops, prototyping, ethnography, and democratic design methods.

LLs provide the methodological and spatial infrastructure to translate QH principles into actionable cultural innovation. In other words, the QH tells who should collaborate, and LLs shows how to make it happen in practice.

Cultural Living Labs and Cultural Hubs

When applied to cultural and heritage contexts, LLs are termed Cultural Living Labs (CLLs). Here, QH partners operate simultaneously as researchers and innovators, bringing together

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

disciplinary knowledge, artistic practices, and cultural expertise ‘in the middle’ to co-produce novel interventions.

EPIC-WE Cultural Hubs are the practical instantiation of this model. They merge the QH innovation framework with LL methodologies, creating spaces for participatory, co-creative, and culturally grounded research and innovation. Cultural Hubs act as both conceptual and practical sites: the QH provides the overarching structure and partnership logic, while LLs enable iterative, real-world testing, co-creation, and experimentation. This dual structure ensures that Cultural Hubs are inclusive, adaptive, and capable of producing culturally meaningful outputs.

The EPIC-WE QH Cultural Hubs in Practice

EPIC-WE QH Cultural Hubs bring together partners from industry, culture, higher education, communications, and civil society, as well as multiple disciplines including games, media, cultural heritage, arts, policy, design, education, and humanities. These diverse sectors and knowledge domains converge to ‘meet in the middle’, collaboratively developing new practices and co-creating cultural innovations (Nørgård and Holflod, 2024).

Roles and responsibilities are clearly delineated:

- CHIs provide cultural heritage, spaces, and expertise about cultural practices;
- CIs contribute game-making tools, methods, and design knowledge;
- HEIs supply research frameworks, education, and culturally-sensitive methodologies;
- YCs offer insights, creativity, and lived experience, shaping game worlds and environments to maximise societal and cultural value.

Overview of the three Cultural Hubs and four helices

While youth as the fourth helix is pivotal, operationalising this role presents challenges. Previous research shows ambiguities in defining and integrating civil society within QH models (Hasche et al., 2020; Schütz et al., 2019). EPIC-WE addresses this by embedding

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

youth partnership and participation systematically in the QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem, the QH Cultural Hubs, and the CGJs, making it both a subject of study and a practical method of innovation.

Within the QH Cultural Hubs, partners engage in iterative cycles of design, testing, and reflection, in the project with a focus on organising CGJs that combine game-making and cultural heritage exploration. The Cultural Hubs serve as dynamic labs, where knowledge cultures cross-pollinate, methods are exchanged, and shared practices emerge. By situating innovation in authentic, real-world contexts, Cultural Hubs enable practical experimentation while maintaining rigorous attention to cultural, social, and ethical dimensions.

Ultimately, the EPIC-WE QH Cultural Hubs function as living, adaptive ecosystems where all four helices collaborate on equal footing. The approach strengthens cultural partnerships, extends societal roles, and demonstrates how youth, educational, creative, and heritage sectors can co-create culture in transformative ways.

Structure and Methods of this report

In this report, we will show how we have applied and adapted the Quadruple Helix Ecosystem to Living Lab practice through the lifespan of the project from 2023 to 2025 (although it continues into 2026) to develop, implement, and test QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystems and QH Cultural Hubs. We do this based on the six principles that were previously established in the [D3.3, Report on Insights from the Design and Construction of Ecosystems and Game Jams](#) on insights from the design and construction of ecosystems and CGJs. These principles identify and determine the foundational principles for the formation and running of QH Cultural Hubs. For each principle, we will explain the intention (explanation), how we implemented it (experience), and what our reflection on it is (reflection). The principles are:

- Principle 1: Democratize cultural innovation by including citizens and users as core partners in the QH Cultural Hub;
- Principle 2: Form equal and transformative partnerships in cultural innovation;
- Principle 3: Institute meeting in the middle;
- Principle 4: Practice co-creative cultural innovation and transformation for public good(s);
- Principle 5: Develop real-world, real-life QH Cultural Hubs;
- Principle 6: Advance Empowered Participation in Culture.

The explanation, experience and reflection sections of this report have been written on the basis of several sources. Firstly, various project publications were used, such as D3.1, D3.2 and D3.3, as well as several research papers (see references). Care was taken to ensure that the information in this deliverable is consistent with D4.1, Report on Game-Making

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

Interventions with Youth in Cultural Heritage Institutions, which was written simultaneously with D4.2. Secondly, all Cultural Hub partners were asked to complete a worksheet in which they reflected on the six principles and their different components. Partner Lúsofona University completed these worksheets together with their Youth Advisory Board (YAB) members. The quotes from partners included in this deliverable originate from these worksheets.

Finally, in order to incorporate the Youth Citizen perspective in this deliverable, two in-depth interviews were conducted with the young people leading the Aarhus and Hilversum YABs. These will be referenced several times throughout this report, as the insights from these interviews are exemplary of the YAB process and how it is perceived by these two YAB members. In addition to these interviews, references will be made to examples of experiences with YAB members that were encountered or observed during the project by various Cultural Hub members and described by them in their worksheets.

PRINCIPLE

01

Democratize cultural innovation by including citizens and users as core partners in the QH Cultural Hub

Principle 1: Democratize cultural innovation by including citizens and users as core partners in the QH Cultural Hub

In the QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem, citizens/users are central partners in cultural research and innovation. As **equal partners** and **active co-creators** within the QH Cultural Hub and in its execution of cultural events such as Cultural Game Jams, citizens/users engage in research and innovation on an equal footing with the other helix partners. Equal participation among cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, higher education institutions and citizens/users ensures that cultural transformation and innovation remain democratic, authentic, credible, and impactful. The QH Cultural Hub model fosters democratic and participatory co-creation by **embedding citizens/users at every phase**, enabling them to participate meaningfully in research and innovation activities as a deliberate form of culture-making.

Explanation

In principle 1, '*citizens and users*' are seen as central partners in cultural research and innovation. But who do we mean by '*citizens and users*' within EPIC-WE? In our project, the most important collaboration happens with young people (aged 16 to 25), since they constitute the fourth helix partner of our QH Cultural Hub. Originally, the project aimed to include Youth Citizens (YCs) as participants in the Cultural Game Jams (CGJs), with the participants acting as co-creators of the research outputs (in the form of written game logs and the creation of games through and for culture) as well as iterative testing and evaluation of the CGJ interventions. However, as mentioned in the introduction, literature shows that integrating civil society – YCs in the case of the EPIC-WE project – in the QH ecosystem is not an easy task. To create genuine equal participation, we felt, quite early and strongly during the evolution of the project, the need to involve young people in a more demanding and sincere way than merely as participants in the CGJs. This led to the establishment of both local Youth Advisory Boards in the three QH Cultural Hubs as well as YAB members serving as experts on an equal footing with the other experts on the project's Advisory Board. These developments will be reflected upon throughout this report, and in this first principle in particular.

While we also worked with other '*citizens*' throughout the project, such as external professionals acting as jury members or giving guest lectures during CGJs, the focus remains on youth since they form the fourth partner in our Quadruple Helix Cultural Hub model. By embedding youth in every phase of the project and aiming to position them as equal partners and active co-creators, the traditional boundaries and divides between research and practice were both blurred and reconfigured.

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

Experience

As previously explained, a quadruple helix entails collaboration between four different sectors who not only pursue a shared goal but also engage collectively in exploring and problematising the world around them. It represents a space that is as much about inquiry and reflection as it is about achieving results. In the context of the EPIC-WE project, youth constituted the fourth helix partner, taking shape both as participants in the CGJs and as members of the Youth Advisory Boards (YABs). It is important to stress here that, although the name Youth Advisory Board might suggest that young people only *advised* us, this was not the case in practice. Beyond giving advice, they were actively involved in co-shaping, co-organising and supporting the CGJs. They did this, for example, by providing support in the form of facilitation, providing feedback on new ideas, designing the planning, or evaluating the CGJs. In addition, they also played an active role in various project activities, including:

- Outreach and communication and dissemination efforts (e.g., public presentations at Next Library or giving interviews published on the EPIC-WE Project Website);
- Co-authoring research publications and presentations (e.g. ECGBL2025);
- Leading and participating in capacity-building workshops and policy panels (e.g. EYE2025) aimed at external stakeholders and policy-makers.

This evolution of the YABs and youth as partners reflects a broader commitment within EPIC-WE to embed youth perspectives at all levels of the project, from conceptual development to public engagement.

For this first principle, as well as for the rest of this deliverable, it is useful to first explain how the Youth Advisory Boards were created in each Cultural Hub and how they worked in practice. Across the Cultural Hubs, following the organisation of the first CGJ(s), there was a strong drive to involve young people not only through reflection and research moments during the CGJ, but more closely in the project and in the process of shaping the CGJs. The chosen approach was to set up YABs, composed of young people who had either participated in a previous CGJ or were affiliated with one of the Cultural Hub partners.

The YAB initiative arose from a proposal by the Aarhus Cultural Hub to the project's Executive Board, advocating for the formal inclusion of youth as active fourth partners within the cultural quadruple helix model. Building on this first principle, which emphasises the inclusion of citizens and users as core partners in the QH Cultural Hub, there was a clear intention and desire to ensure that youth voices were included in the processes, not just in the results. The proposal therefore emphasised the importance of youth participation not just as contributors, but as co-creators in shaping cultural innovation.

In early 2024, the Aarhus Cultural Hub established the first EPIC-WE YAB, with its initial three members selected from the inaugural CGJ held in Aarhus. These Youth Citizens were

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

recruited by the Aarhus Cultural Hub Lead based on the leads' talks with these participants during the CGJs and their interest in participating in the project. They were selected for their diverse disciplinary and professional backgrounds, including expertise in game design and programming, arts, culture, design, interactive media, and youth cultures and identities. This diversity was seen as a strength, with strong connections to the project's cross-sectors 'meeting in the middle' aims and structure, providing a wide range of perspectives and experiences among the board members. Later, the YAB was extended by recruiting international Youth Citizens, making the YAB both Danish and "global".

From its inception, the YAB was guided by two core principles:

- Organic Growth: Youth partnership was designed to expand naturally through open invitations extended during subsequent CGJs;
- Youth-Led Engagement: The YABs were empowered to define their own roles, choosing the content, processes, and areas of the project they wished to engage with.

The Cultural Hub Leader played a facilitative role from the outset, providing practical support in organising meetings, maintaining communication between the YAB and other project partners, and ensuring that youth voices were regarded as equal to those of different stakeholders.

Importantly, participation in the Aarhus YAB has been entirely voluntary, with no financial compensation (similarly to the other experts serving on the EPIC-WE Advisory Board). However, members have gained significant non-monetary benefits, including access to professional networks, project activities and events, professional skill development, meaningful sector relationships, and valuable culture and game experiences. The question of how to recognise and reward youth involvement and agency has remained a central theme in ongoing discussions, iterations, and enactments of the YAB model.

From the subsequent CGJs, the Aarhus YAB expanded to five members, and later to six. During this time, several discussions took place with the board about how youth could gain genuine agency, empowerment, and influence within the project. As a result, each EPIC-WE QH Cultural Hub first established a local YAB and then each local YAB were invited to have one representative serve as youth representative and expert on the project's Advisory Board, recognising their critical expertise and giving youth a formal voice in strategic decision-making.

In Óbidos, a YAB was created after the first two CGJs and brought together six young people: two youth researchers from the project and four bachelor students from Lusófona University. The selection process followed two steps: first, a recruitment form was sent to several students from communication sciences and arts bachelor's degrees. After that, both the

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

coordinator and two young researchers selected a few students for an interview, to be able to assess the English skills of each student, as well as their background related to citizenship in their communities. After the interviews, four youth were selected for the YAB by the coordinator and the two young researchers. The youth researchers being part of the YAB, supported by research scholarships, conducted interviews, data analysis, and observations during the CGJs. Their involvement ensured proximity to the CGJ participants, who felt more at ease engaging with them. The four bachelor's students joined the YAB voluntarily, gaining curricular experience. They also participated in CGJs, both as game-makers and as advisors to other participants, collecting valuable insights that would otherwise have been missed. During the final CGJ, the Óbidos YAB really took charge, as two YAB members were the ones selecting the CGJ theme and acting as facilitators, which is a good example of how the YAB represented youth wants.

In Hilversum, participants from CGJ#1 were asked if they would be interested in joining a YAB. This led to the formation of an initial group of 5 people, which was later expanded to include 4 participants from CGJ#3 who worked on a specific research assignment developed together with one of the HEI members. One other YC joined the Hilversum YAB after one of the initial YAB members shared their experience with this YC (a classmate), which sparked interest and ultimately led to that classmate joining the Hilversum YAB.

The Hilversum Cultural Hub sought to ensure that the YAB was treated as equal partners by involving them in every phase of the project, as the principle states. In practice, this meant including the YAB before, during, and after the CGJs. Beforehand, they contributed to shaping themes, recruiting participants, and designing the programme. This was done by keeping them informed via email, inviting them to online team meetings, or joining physical Design Sprint sessions with the other Cultural Hub partners.

During the CGJs, tasks were discussed with the young people in advance to see where their interests lay. For example, one preferred to support the research team with observations, while another joined the communications team by recording testimonials or serving as a jury member in the evaluation of games.

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

Two YAB members (right left and left left) taking part in the Hilversum CGJ#2 and CGJ#4 as jury members

Reflection

The goal of this first principle was to ensure that young people were active co-creators, and that their voices truly mattered. One of the reflection questions we asked the YAB members was whether they felt involved in each stage of the co-creation process. Both members interviewed indicated that this was not entirely the case. The Aarhus YAB member stated that she did not feel involved in the actual planning of the CGJs, even though she would have liked to be. The Hilversum YAB member had a similar experience, noting that ‘often, it felt like we were invited to share our opinions only once most ideas and plans were already prepared, which made it harder to influence bigger decisions.’ Conversely, she did feel strongly involved in the actual execution of the CGJs, although she would have preferred to be more included in the aftermath of the jam, during which reflections and discussions took place about how the event had gone. She explained that this phase would have been particularly valuable to observe how experiences and feedback shaped future decisions, how researchers developed their outputs based on the CGJs, and that it would even have been interesting to act as assistants in this process.

Reflections on this principle were also provided from the perspective of the other three sectors, and the dominant tendency across all QH Cultural Hubs was that examples can be found of changes made as a direct result of YAB feedback – changes that would not have occurred if they had only been passive spectators. One example from the Hilversum Cultural Hub came during a design sprint session in preparation for CGJ#3. The Cultural Hub team meeting was split into two groups (research and content) with a YAB member in each. Within the content team, the YAB participant proposed a brilliant idea for the museum visit, based on his own experience during CGJ#1, which was then developed further and successfully implemented in practice.

“ [Young people are at the heart of the project](#) ”

- Filmby Aarhus

Ensuring that youth were equal partners also aligns with the ambition of not only ‘researching about, but researching with.’ By involving young people as researchers – for example, conducting observations during CGJs or carrying out interviews – this ambition was realised in practice. The Óbidos Cultural Hub noted that when youth researchers conducted interviews, the young participants felt more comfortable and spoke more openly about their experiences.

In Hilversum, involving the YAB in research brought some challenges, which in turn became learning opportunities. During CGJ#3, several YAB members wanted to help with

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

observations. They were given the observation forms to complete during the jam. However, in the evaluation afterwards, they mentioned that it was not clear to them what the research was for, which made filling in the forms difficult. To address this, an extra meeting was organised to explain how the research results would be used.

Another key reflection came from Lusófona University, where the YAB ended up being much more represented by the two youth researchers, than the other members. The reason for this lies in the fact that the two youth researchers were employed by the university and working full-time for the project, making it logistically easier to include them in meetings. Contrariwise, the other YAB members were students, working voluntarily for the board, which meant they had to balance academic life and personal life with their participation. Because it felt unfair to ask for the same level of work, the Óbidos Cultural Hub did not always consult the 4 student members, which limited the diversity of ideas. Apart from theme selection, the YAB was not consulted on organisation, logistics, or pre-game jam activities. This shows that involving young people as equal partners is not a straightforward path – it involves ‘failing forward’ as well as multiple iterations.

Although much of the focus so far has been on the Youth Advisory Boards, it is also important to highlight the young people who participated in the CGJs themselves. Here too, the principle was about creating an equal environment. A reflection from Lusófona University (UL) illustrates this well: they described how equality was particularly evident during shared mealtimes between participants and organisers. These moments created a strong sense of community and were emblematic of the CGJs more broadly, which were characterised by a horizontal and relaxed environment.

Conclusion

Principle 1 challenged the CHIs, CIs and HEIs in the QH Cultural Hubs to move beyond positioning youth as end-users in the project and inviting them to participate in the CGJs towards recognising them as co-creators and equal partners in shaping the QH Cultural Hubs, CGJs and their resulting games through and for culture. Across the three Cultural Hubs, this took shape through the active involvement of young participants in the CGJs, inviting them to participate as QH partners in meetings in the QH Cultural Hubs and including them as experts in the Youth Advisory Boards. Their roles went far beyond ‘advising’: they co-designed events and activities, facilitated sessions, carried out research, created games, and inspired ideas that were directly implemented.

At the same time, the process showed that genuine co-creation and partnership is complex and iterative. Questions of representation, balance, voice, and recognition required ongoing reflection, with each Cultural Hub developing its own approach to supporting and rewarding youth engagement. Despite these differences, all Cultural Hubs demonstrated that youth involvement made the project stronger, more relevant, and more democratic.

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

From co-creating cultural experiences to serving as experts and representing EPIC-WE in events, young people demonstrated the transformative power of being trusted as co-creators. Their participation – in both formal and informal settings – highlighted how collaboration flourishes when roles, responsibilities, and perspectives are shared on equal footing.

By embedding youth before, during, and after the CGJs, the project blurred the traditional boundaries between ‘researcher’, ‘innovator’, and ‘participant’. In doing so, it not only upheld the principle of democratising cultural innovation but also created empowering environments where young people experienced genuine ownership, agency, and belonging.

PRINCIPLE

02

**Form equal and
transformative
partnerships in cultural
innovation**

Principle 2: Form equal and transformative partnerships in cultural innovation

QH Cultural Hubs are intentionally designed as **diverse and inclusive environments** where cross sector collaboration and **co-creation** flourish. They are based on the principle that each sector is an **equal partner** in cultural research and innovation and that each partner is **open to being transformed** by the others to 'think, do, and be otherwise' by transcending sectorial boundaries and methods. Each partner must embrace reciprocal transformation through the mutual integration of 'alien' knowledge, values, and meanings discourses.

Explanation

What does openness to being transformed mean? Within this second principle it implies that every sector and partner is willing to do things differently than they would normally do within their own methods, structures, and routines. It is not just about working together, but about being open to becoming changed by and learning from others. While the operationalization of it is difficult and challenging, the intention is that all partners are equal in this process, and each should be open to being transformed by the perspectives, methods, values, and knowledges of the others. As one of our project partners put it: 'The assumption that the four different worlds can come together and create something that is larger and better than each sector could create on their own, is in many ways the essence of EPIC-WE'. In other words, real and transformative innovation happens when we move beyond our own boundaries and create something together that we could not do on our own. The sum is larger than its parts.

Experience

An important part of collaboration is taking time to meet and discuss together. Across the three Cultural Hubs this was organised in different ways. In Aarhus, all four sectors came together on a regular basis, mostly leading up to the intervention (CGJ) in a sprint-inspired approach. During the period between interventions, they came together in more formal meetings (online or on-site), with flexible ad hoc meetings during those months if necessary. This created continuous exchange, learning, and a build-up of shared value, knowledge, and appreciation. In Hilversum, meetings were held every two weeks, and young people were not present at every session. This was a conscious choice, as the Hilversum Cultural Hub wanted to respect the youth's busy schedules. Instead, young people were invited to join when key decisions had to be made – such as choosing the theme of the Cultural Game Jam (CGJ) – or at moments that were most engaging for them, like shaping the CGJ's content. The situation in Aarhus was slightly different, as one of the young participants from an earlier CGJ afterwards was employed first by Filmby Aarhus and then by Aarhus University, taking part

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

in the Cultural Hub meetings, while simultaneously serving on the Aarhus YAB, ensuring integration of youth voices and perspectives.

In Óbidos, meetings happened both in-person and online, but were more sparse. Looking back, the team there felt that more online meetings would have made communication easier and more effective. Aarhus partners also noted that regular meetings beyond the CGJ periods would have been useful. In Hilversum, by contrast, the workflow leaned more on online meetings, with only occasional in-person gatherings and some reliance on email. For all partners there, this balance proved to be a pleasant and practical way of working together.

As stated in this second principle, QH Cultural Hubs are intentionally designed as diverse and inclusive environments where cross sector collaboration and co-creation flourish. In the reflection below, we will consider both the co-creation process within the QH Cultural Hubs and the co-creation element that these Cultural Hubs sought to implement in the design of the CGJs. In the case of the CGJs, young game makers were always placed in the driver's seat. We deliberately tried to avoid being too prescriptive in assigning specific cultural materials or ways of designing games, so that it would not become too much of a 'top-down' approach. As a project, we consistently valued ensuring that the young participants had real agency over their own choices. We experimented with different balances between agency and prescriptive methods to see which approaches led to greater confidence, empowerment, and meaningful outcomes. This was reflected, for example, in the choice of the CGJ theme, which was deliberately abstract and flexible enough to be approached from multiple perspectives.

Reflection

Looking back at our collaboration within the QH Cultural Hub, several points stand out. First, working in an interdisciplinary field meant that preexisting methods and knowledges as well as existing sector or partner frameworks – sometimes more rigid, sometimes more flexible – were constantly challenged. This required adaptability from all helix partners. As the ARoS art museum explained, there were 'many constraints' within their organisation, which made it difficult at times 'to think, do, and be otherwise'. Yet in a project like this, the key is to keep trying, to keep looking for solutions, to keep collaborating in order to succeed. The Portuguese CI partner Battlesheep captured this spirit well:

“Success was only possible with all perspectives considered ”

- Battlesheep

Second, the Hilversum Cultural Hub experienced that when a team brings together people with many different skills, the division of work and task ownership can sometimes become muddy and unclear. In their Cultural Hub, much of the work around both creation and execution were highly integrated and collaborative. Because the Amsterdam University of

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

Applied Sciences (AUAS) team is part of the Visual Methodologies Collective, their researchers – though focused on the project’s research tasks – were deeply involved in content creation. They greatly valued the perspectives and knowledge shared by archives and creatives, as their own expertise lies in visualisation and content development. At the same time, the cultural partner Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision (NISV) had two team members with strong backgrounds in games, who were able to ‘code-switch’ between sectors and show how game methodologies could enrich cultural approaches, and vice versa. While this sometimes blurred the lines between roles and responsibilities, it ultimately led to refreshing ideas and a unique form of collaboration.

An AUAS researcher observing (left) and acting as a facilitator (right) during Hilversum CGJ#4

This issue surrounding task ownership was not experienced by the other Cultural Hubs in Óbidos or Aarhus. In Óbidos, roles and responsibilities were clearly defined, and also within the Cultural Hub partners themselves – such as among the researchers – tasks were well distributed. At least three researchers took care of observations during the four CGJs, as well as surveys, GDPR and interviews. Another researcher, also a YAB member, was responsible for managing Discord and itch.io, while someone else handled communication and dissemination. In the Aarhus Cultural Hub, the diversity of skills did not lead to problems; rather, it was the differences in organisation and organisational structures – such as varying organisational rhythms, approaches, processes, and divisions of labour – that at times proved difficult to navigate.

Thirdly, YAB members indicated in their reflections that they would have liked to have had even more influence over certain decisions. Particularly in the lead-up to a new CGJ, they did not always feel sufficiently involved or informed about what was happening – despite being present and actively participating in meetings – or they were involved only after certain decisions had already been made, leaving limited room for substantial changes. From the perspective of the other helix partners, this may indicate that we were overly cautious, attempting not to overwhelm the YAB members given their already busy schedules with studies and part-time jobs or that there were project obligations or constraints not allowing for the changes desired by the YABs. In hindsight, we could have placed clearer roles and

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

responsibilities with the YAB itself to indicate what level of involvement was possible for them. Like for the rest of the partners in the EPIC-WE project, far from everything is possible given what was promised in the Grant Agreement for the Europe Horizon project.

One of the YAB-members (left) providing feedback to a participant during Hilversum CGJ#4

Fourthly, in terms of co-creation in the lead up to the CGJs, an example of how the QH Cultural Hubs applied co-creation, a Hilversum Cultural Hub YAB member mentions a preparation session for CGJ#3 she attended. The Cultural Hub was divided into two groups ('content' and 'research') to effectively discuss the CGJ program. This YAB member joined the "research" group because she found it the most interesting, and she says it was very inspiring for her to see how ideas were being created collaboratively, with everyone building on each other's input. For her, this was a clear moment of co-creation because the atmosphere showed both collective responsibility and genuine joy in shaping the outcome together. It felt like a space where different perspectives merged seamlessly into one shared direction.

“ Co-creation is not just about dividing tasks, but about genuinely exchanging perspectives, respecting each other's input and shaping the process collectively ”

- Hilversum Cultural Hub YAB member

When it comes to co-creation during the CGJs, the Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences, within the Hilversum Cultural Hub, reflected that in the beginning they went all out and did way too much, leading to an overwhelming array of methods and formats. These eventually had to be reduced in the following jams. They also decided to bring the CGJ themes closer to home, focusing on topics such as climate. Flexibility, they emphasised, proved to be key. Depending on the group of participants, the execution of methods had to be adjusted. For instance, there was a marked difference in how 16-year-old high school

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

students approached documentation compared to third-year university students.

Lusófona University also noted an interesting distinction regarding age groups. In their CGJs they worked with participants spanning different age brackets, including both high school and university students. They observed that the dynamic between these groups sometimes required more careful facilitation in order to ensure equitable participation across varying skill and knowledge levels. In particular, there was a noticeable asymmetry between university and high school participants. It often proved difficult to foster interaction between the two, which led to a division: although they shared the same space, the groups showed little interest in engaging with one another. During CGJ#3 and CGJ#4, even though pre-jam activities were organised to break the ice, participants once again split into two distinct clusters – university students on one side and high school students on the other – which only deepened the divide. It is also important to note that during all four game jams, game-making workshops were conducted to assure that high school students, with less skills, could still learn enough to develop a prototype and apply their knowledge.

Finally, the requirements and workloads within the Cultural Hub turned out to be numerous and at times difficult to manage. Although several plans were co-created for activities, publications, events, and dissemination, more pragmatic approaches would have been preferable. Such approaches would have better respected and protected the participants of the Cultural Hub, while also securing spaces for innovation that are deliberately slow, reflective, and thoughtful.

Conclusion

Our work with this principle showed that genuine collaboration goes far beyond coordinating efforts – it requires a willingness to be changed by the perspectives, values, and working methods of others. Within the QH Cultural Hubs, this meant that each partner had to step outside their own sector habits and comfort zones to create a shared space for collaboration and co-creation. Collaboration became a process of learning to ‘think, do, and be otherwise,’ where different disciplines, sectors, and generations continuously influenced and transformed one another. At times, this required navigating structural constraints, blurred roles, and uneven participation, but these very challenges also fostered transformative creativity and deeper understanding. Through everyday practices and continuous engagement and dialogue, partners discovered that transformation does not occur in the absence of tension, but through it.

At the same time, the experience of co-shaping the project revealed that equal and transformative partnerships depend on mutual trust, communication, and the recognition of each sector's and partner's unique contribution. Across the QH Cultural Hubs, this was practiced in diverse ways – from weekly interdisciplinary meetings to informal exchanges and creative co-working sessions. Even when differences in methods, structures or working

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

rhythms created friction, they also sparked moments of co-shaped research and innovation. Importantly, the process was a reminder that true equality is not a static endpoint but continually engendered and negotiated: it involves listening, adjusting, and being open to influence and transformation. When collaboration moves beyond cooperation and becomes a reciprocal process of change, it generates a kind of cultural innovation that no single sector or partner could achieve on their own.

The co-creation elements within the CGJs provided a concrete example of this principle in action. By deliberately giving young participants real agency over decision, from shaping content to choosing themes, the Cultural Hubs created spaces where multiple perspectives could merge and evolve together. Moments of co-creation within the QH Cultural Hubs themselves were marked not by task division, but by the collective generation of ideas, mutual learning, and shared responsibility for outcomes. Challenges such as differing skill levels, age groups, and participation rhythms required careful facilitation, yet these very dynamics enriched the process and highlighted the value of flexibility, reflection, and experimentation. Ultimately, the CGJs demonstrated that empowering participants as co-creators – rather than merely as contributors to predefined outcomes – deepens engagement, fosters confidence, and produces innovative results that reflect the collective input of all partners.

PRINCIPLE

03

**Institute meetings in
the middle**

Principle 3: Institute meetings in the middle

QH Cultural Hubs deliberately establish themselves by 'meeting in the middle.' They serve as the operational space for cross-sector transformative partnerships. These meetings necessitate that all partners 'meet each other halfway' regarding vocabularies, ideas, methodologies, practices, and expectations. QH Cultural Hubs, enacted through 'meetings in the middle,' promote ongoing dynamic negotiation, enabling the reimagination and reconfiguration of cultural practices. This, in turn, demands resilience and commitment from all sector partners as it disrupts the stable and stabilises the unstable to create new forms of cultural collaboration that transcend traditional sectoral divides.

Explanation

As visible in the title and description of this principle, 'meeting in the middle' is a vital part of this principle, but what does it mean? 'Meeting in the middle' specifically means that each partner, and the QH Cultural Hub as a whole, extend themselves into an open, liminal 'third space' for becoming someone and something else together while keeping the sectoral and professional expertise and nuance each partner represents and adds to this middle. It implies that each sector and partner is open to working in ways that might differ considerably from what they are used to and understanding that while it might take longer to form a common vision or strategy, it will likely be more impactful and innovative by embracing this 'in the middle' and 'third space.' Rather than focusing on individual interests, the QH Cultural Hub promotes the development and enactment of an environment where all knowledges, perspectives, and voices are acknowledged and come together towards shared values, ambitions, and objectives.

This can be both a potential and challenge. It requires partners to balance two things at once: staying true to their professional expertise, organisational routines, and disciplinary perspectives, while also being open to change, experimentation, and collaboration. The tension between these aspects can create friction, but it is precisely this friction that allows moments of shared understanding, transformation, and innovation to emerge.

In practice, the principle of 'meeting in the middle' means that no single partner 'owns the middle,' sets the agenda, or dictates the terms of collaboration. Instead, all participants, as described in principle 6, are co-owners of the QH Cultural Hub and bear responsibility for adapting their vocabularies, methods, and expectations to each other so that meaningful communication and joint action become possible. This requires an ongoing process of translation and negotiation, where misunderstandings and frictions are seen not as barriers but as opportunities to rethink established ways of working. Such collaboration demands

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

resilience and commitment to ‘stay with the trouble’, as it often disturbs familiar taken-for-granted routines while also providing possibilities for experimental and new emerging practices. By simultaneously disrupting sector/partner stability and stabilising the unstable co-owned ‘middle’, partners create a middle ground where new cultural collaboration practices and their resulting innovative products materialise.

Experience

This third principle was implemented through iterative experiments with roles, responsibilities, and ways of participating within the Cultural Hub, which was part of enabling new approaches to joint and co-creative work. From the beginning, we had a designated Cultural Hub leader responsible for coordinating efforts, having partners meet in the middle, mitigating the emerging tensions and challenges, translating requests from the ‘larger project’ to the ‘local practices’ to support both Cultural Hub participants and working conditions, and in planning ‘in the middle’ meetings, Cultural Hub activities, and seeking to promote a caring cross-sector environment. Concretely, there were many discussions and negotiations of what it might mean to extend oneself towards this new ‘middle ground’ and to others – and how, in a professional and innovative environment, this also comes with challenges in navigating the rhythms, divisions of labour, and routines of different sectors and partners.

This aligned with the specific example provided by the Óbidos Cultural Hub, explaining how all Cultural Hub partners were consistently kept ‘in the loop’ in email correspondence throughout the project, even when sometimes it felt as though the topic was outside the scope of their sector.

Although this was also the case in the Hilversum Cultural Hub, it was specifically emphasised there that there was also a strong sense of trust:

“ We work on the basis of trust and transdisciplinarity meaning we do not always have to meet halfway but trust on the expertise of the partners (and they on ours) ”

- Amsterdam University of Applied Science

In practice, this meant that while partners kept each other informed about their activities through updates in meetings or by email, there was also a strong degree of mutual trust that each partner would carry out their responsibilities effectively. A possible explanation for this being highlighted specifically within the Hilversum Cultural Hub is that the three Cultural Hub partners had already established a ‘middle ground’ through earlier collaboration on other projects and as a result were able to extend the middle through building on those existing relationships.

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

Reflection

Meeting in the middle meant that whenever partners disagreed on certain matters, we held well-reasoned and civilised discussions to find solutions we could all accept. We listened to one another, showed mutual respect, and collaborated as equals between CHI, CI and HEI. At the same time, it also meant being able to hold on to differences and tensions without immediately resolving them. Inspired by Readings' notion of 'communities of dissensus', we recognised that disagreement can be generative, providing space for reflection and new ideas. From a Bakhtinian perspective, collaboration involves a dynamic interplay between forces that pull towards agreement and forces that push towards openness and exploration. In practice, this meant continuously negotiating between staying true to one's own knowledge and perspectives, while remaining open to the ideas, methods, and experiences of others. This tension, rather than being a problem, often became a source of creativity and innovation.

When it came to the involvement of young people, however, meeting each other halfway could perhaps have been more successful. This was a sentiment shared by all three Cultural Hubs. In Hilversum, for example, they noted that sometimes a member of the Youth Advisory Board (YAB) would provide feedback that was later overruled by one of the 'professional' partners of the quadruple helix. We listened to the advice and took it into consideration, but at times decided to act differently nonetheless – sometimes for practical reasons (such as budget constraints), and at other times because of the more experienced perspective of team members.

Óbidos also indicated that youth participation was limited in the early stages of the project, as young people were initially recruited only as participants without influence on the structure or themes. The YAB was only established by CGJ#3, and young people only gained genuine decision-making power in the fourth. Earlier involvement would have enabled stronger co-creation and reciprocal learning between youth and partners. Finally, Aarhus stated that stronger integration of the local Youth Advisory Board in the everyday practice of the Aarhus QH Cultural Hub would have been valuable in further empowering young people to become active and engaged participants in "the middle."

An interesting difference between the Cultural Hubs can be found in how research activities were carried out during the CGJs. Beforehand, a fixed set of research tasks had been agreed. After organising the first CGJ, however, it became clear that implementing these research activities (such as conducting interviews or filling in questionnaires) disrupted the workflow of the CGJ process. While Lusófona University stressed that these research tasks were nevertheless essential for capturing learning outcomes, the Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences noted that once it became clear that the CGJ needed to be drastically simplified, the

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

role and position of research had to be renegotiated. They resolved this by integrating research into the overall activities.

This example is instructive for two reasons. Firstly, it demonstrates the value of the iterative character of the CGJs: based on feedback from the first event, it was possible to identify which adjustments were necessary and feasible. Secondly, it shows that 'meeting each other halfway' can take very different forms. Whereas Lusófona University did not see room to adapt the research activities, AUAS chose a more flexible approach and incorporated them differently.

With regards to language and jargon used, the YAB members indicated in their reflections that there was little misunderstanding between helix partners. The partners were very accommodating and communicated effectively with the YAB members. During joint meetings, the Aarhus YAB member did not feel excluded in any way. Even when jargon was used, she felt safe and valued enough to ask for clarification if she did not understand something.

Conclusion

The third principle, *meeting in the middle*, has proven to be both a guiding value and a lived practice across the QH Cultural Hubs. It called for an ongoing willingness to engage each other and be open to transformation – to listen, interpret, and adapt while maintaining mutual respect and trust. In each Cultural Hub, this principle was embodied through joint practices, a shared middle ground, open communication, sector transparency, and confidence in one another's unique expertise. Partners learned that collaboration does not always require full consensus or fully aligned agreement, but rather the shared commitment to remain invested and in dialogue with each other. The ability to negotiate meaning, methods, roles and responsibilities across sectors enabled the creation of new collaboration and co-creation practices that could not have emerged within a single partner, sector, or discipline. This continuous balancing of structure and flexibility became a defining feature of the QH Cultural Hubs' collaborative culture.

At the same time, *meeting in the middle* also revealed its complexities. Youth participation, for instance, showed how balancing professional perspectives with emerging voices requires care and flexibility. Similarly, differences in how research activities were integrated during the CGJs highlighted that there is no single way to 'meet halfway' – sometimes it means adhering to agreed frameworks, while at other times it demands adaptation and creative reconfiguration. Across all contexts, the principle encouraged partners to view friction and disagreement as opportunities for growth rather than obstacles. Ultimately, the Cultural Hubs demonstrated that *meeting in the middle* is not about reaching perfect consensus, but about cultivating a middle ground where difference, dialogue, and disruption coexist productively – allowing transformative collaboration to take root and blossom.

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

PRINCIPLE

04

**Practice co-creative
cultural innovation and
transformation for
public good(s)**

Principle 4: Practice co-creative cultural innovation and transformation for public good(s)

Innovation in QH Cultural Hubs is experimental, iterative, open-ended, and focused on co-creating cultural **public good(s)**. By prioritising co-creation for public good(s) over purely technical, economical, or instrumental solutions, QH Cultural Hubs ensure that cultural goods and innovations remain valuable, meaningful, and **freely accessible** for all. Cultural innovation must serve the public good as public goods, positioning cultural QH Cultural Hubs and Cultural Game Jams as drivers for democratic and empowered cultural participation.

Explanation

How can we ensure that innovation creates public goods and serves the public good? This question lies at the heart of the fourth principle. The focus of this principle is on the creation of public good(s) as the outcome of the practices and partnerships within the Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs (QH Cultural Hubs). To understand this focus, it is first essential to distinguish between public goods and public good, as well as explain the broader concept of the public sphere.

As Aarhus University partners Nørgård and Holflod show in one of the project publications (Nørgård and Holflod, 2024), public goods are created resources or services that are openly available and can be used by many people at the same time without reducing their availability to others. They are typically defined as non-rivalrous (one person's use does not prevent another's) and non-excludable (no one can be prevented from using them). Examples can be a public park, a city library, or – in the case of the EPIC-WE project – the open, online and freely available EPIC-WE [resource website](#) that shows the games through/for culture prototypes, Cultural Game Jam Kit, QH sector testimonials, QH Cultural Hub model and more that were created during the project and consist of creative commons resources for everyone to use.

Public good, in contrast, emphasises collective or joint activities and the public benefits that emerge from them. Public good emphasises the collective value generated by social, cultural, or civic innovation and engagement, such as the creation of a community festival, collaborative storytelling, or – in the case of the EPIC-WE project – engagement in Cultural Hubs and cultural game-making that produces public good in the form of enhanced cultural participation, shared knowledge, and civic agency. Here, the value is generated not solely by the QH Cultural Hubs or CGJs themselves, but by the collaborative process that brings together young citizens, cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, and researchers to

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

co-produce cultural experiences and meaning.

As stated in this fourth principle, cultural innovation must ‘serve the public good as public goods’. This means that cultural innovation must both create tangible resources that are freely accessible to all (public goods) and generate broader cultural and societal value through collaboration and participation (public good).

Finally, the public sphere provides the context in which these interactions take place. It is a social domain characterised by dialogue, deliberation, and inclusive participation, rather than hierarchy, power, or market forces. Historically, this could resemble town hall meetings, whereas in EPIC-WE it is enacted through QH Cultural Hubs, where all four helices collaborate, exchange knowledge, and co-created shared cultural outcomes.

Experience

Throughout the lifespan of the Cultural Hubs, the Cultural Hubs have collaborated on sharing materials, resources, and experiences across various spaces – including creative industries, cultural heritage institutions, and higher education and academia. The emphasis on dissemination within the Cultural Hubs has resulted in a high output of accessible public goods, increased citizen engagement, and broader communication to relevant audiences.

A key outcome of an open-innovation for public good initiative is the open and creative commons EPIC-WE resource website. On this website the resources produced throughout the project are displayed, with a focus on all the cultural game prototypes that were developed during the twelve Cultural Game Jams (CGJs). The aim is to provide insight into the thinking and creation process behind the development of these prototypes, so that it can help others who wish to organise their own CGJ. This way, the website serves as an outcome of ‘open innovation for public good’, where design-kits, game prototypes, guides and other materials created during the project’s cultural game-jam and youth-empowerment activities are gathered and made freely available to organisations, educators and young people who want to replicate or learn from the project’s ecosystem.

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

Cultural Game Prototypes showcased on the EPIC-WE resource website

In addition to publishing this resource website, the EPIC-WE project has also continuously shared research results, games, and reports with the wider public throughout the project – rather than only doing so at the end of the project. For example, this included sharing research findings during events (and actively involving the audience in discussions about these findings) as well as publishing academic papers throughout the course of the project.

Reflection

Reflecting on the role of the public good/public goods throughout the EPIC-WE project, it becomes clear that the ambition of creating public good(s) was embedded in every Cultural Hub. Nevertheless, it proved challenging to sustain the focus on the public good(s) amid the fast-paced, hands-on reality of running CGJs. Much of the Cultural Hubs' time and energy went into facilitating participation, managing logistics, and supporting creative production. Although we did our best to publish as many of the results as possible during the project itself, translating those rich outputs into lasting and shareable public goods sometimes happened later or not at all.

When reflecting on working within the Quadruple Helix system, this structure proved to be both demanding and valuable. The QH required reconciling different expectations of what constitutes a useful resource. Researchers often valued documentation and frameworks, creative industry partners emphasised design and usability, while youth participants cared most about the immediacy of making and play. Despite the fact that navigating between these differing perspectives was demanding, this mix of viewpoints ultimately ensured that the public goods we did create – such as the open resource website and design kits – were more inclusive and accessible than if any one group had worked in isolation. This demonstrates the value of the QH system.

However, this diversity of perspectives also led to some unevenness. This is evident, for example, in the use of the platform itch.io – an online platform where creators can publish, share, and sell independent video games and digital projects directly to players. Because of its strong embedding in the gaming world, the EPIC-WE project chose to use this platform to enable participants to document their process. The intention was for them to create so-called 'game logs' at various stages during the CGJs. However, when the Hilversum Cultural Hub collaborated with a secondary school class of sixteen-year-olds during CGJ#2, it became clear that they were unable to fully complete the itch.io pages. Some pages therefore remained unfinished because the resource platform was not perceived as meaningful by the Youth Citizens themselves. Their primary goal was to complete their game prototypes, not to contribute to a long-term archive. This highlights an important lesson: to make co-created outputs truly public goods, their value needs to be visible and relevant to all contributors from the very beginning.

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

Looking ahead, one of the most important insights from the QH Cultural Hubs is that the process of co-creation is itself a form of public good, even when tangible products remain incomplete. The relationships, shared methods, and mutual understanding developed through collaboration form the foundation for sustainable, ethical, and democratic cultural innovation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Principle 4 highlights that cultural innovation grounded in co-creation for public good(s) can transform how we understand and practise participation in both the creative industry, higher education, and cultural sector. Through the Quadruple Helix approach, the EPIC-WE project demonstrates that innovation flourishes when diverse sectors collaborate openly and equitably towards the creation of public goods, contributing their distinct perspectives, expertise, and products. The project's commitment to producing both public goods (tangible, freely accessible resources such as the open EPIC-WE resource website) and public good (the shared value generated through collective creativity and civic QH engagement) shows that cultural innovation can serve society beyond economic or technological aims. By embedding the creation of public good(s) into every QH Cultural Hub, EPIC-WE affirmed the importance of making research and innovation a space of inclusion, co-creation, empowerment, and democratic exchange.

At the same time, the experience of the QH Cultural Hubs revealed the complexities of sustaining this ambition in practice. Balancing co-creation with the demands of formal project requirements and deliverables required ongoing negotiation between researchers, creative professionals, cultural heritage institutions, and youth citizens. The unevenness observed in certain activities, such as the use of the itch.io platform by different types of participants, underscores that for co-created outcomes to become genuine public goods, their purpose and value must resonate with all contributors from the outset. Nevertheless, the project's collaborative processes, relationships, and shared learning represent enduring forms of public good. They offer a model for how co-creative cultural innovation can continue to inspire ethical, inclusive, and sustainable transformation well beyond the project's lifespan.

PRINCIPLE

05

Develop real-world, real-life QH Cultural Hub

Principle 5: Develop real-world, real-life QH Cultural Hubs

QH Cultural Hubs are established and operate within larger existing (global-glocal-local) cultural ecosystems. As such, QH Cultural Hubs are naturally part of and take part in the **everyday real-life of real-world spaces** such as museums, libraries, cultural centres, public spaces, and heritage sites. Rather than erecting external ‘innovation spaces’, QH Cultural Hub partners use their **cultural homes** to practice co-design transformation in collaboration with local citizens, users, and stakeholders. This requires that these spaces be **reconfigured** to be collectively occupied and acted on by the QH Cultural Hub partners, transforming and de-centring traditional institutional frameworks and spaces to allow new modes of living, acting, and being together within a shared, participatory environment.

Explanation

‘An everyday real-life of real-world spaces’ can take many forms. What did this look like within the EPIC-WE project? In the project, we applied this principle by making use of existing networks and the physical spaces of our CGJ sites and Cultural Hubs. This makes the Cultural Hubs both tangible, physical spaces, manifested in ‘the homes’ of the sector partners (e.g. meetings at ARoS, Filmbym Aarhus or Aarhus University in the Aarhus QH Cultural Hub) and in the Cultural Game Jam event (taking place at the cultural heritage sites of Obidós, Hilversum, and Aarhus) as well as intangible, virtual spaces. For example, the tangible spaces were manifested in the everyday practices of the QH Cultural Hubs and the festive events of Cultural Game Jams (CGJs) where participants gathered to co-create games in museums and cultural heritage sites. Meanwhile, the virtual spaces emerged through the use of online platforms and shared digital environments where ideas, narratives, and design assets circulated beyond geographical boundaries, such as the use of itch.io to document the co-created game prototypes.

Making use of these tangible, existing places does not mean they are used in the same way as before the QH Cultural Hub came together. On the contrary, the idea is to look within the ‘cultural home’ of a partner at how spaces can be reconfigured and developed, so they can be collectively inhabited and shaped by all partners.

Experience

A clear example of a way in which a ‘cultural home’ was reconfigured, are the first CGJs in Aarhus and Hilversum. During these CGJs, participants stayed overnight in the ARoS Aarhus Art Museum and the Media Museum of the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision (NISV). For both museums, this was the first time people had ever stayed overnight in their venues, providing a clear example of how a museum space was reconfigured into a sleeping space.

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

Overall, many CGJ participants mentioned in their reflections that they found it very inspiring to be in the different cultural venues - and especially the overnight stay was a unique moment to them. One of them, for example, describes the NISV Media Museum as 'the walls that carry the history of the past and the excitement of the future.' She calls the night she spent in the museum during CGJ#1 a true 'night at the museum' experience – although there were no moving exhibits, the time pressure of this weekend CGJ made her team full of energy and stress, thinking nothing would work out. In the end, the museum gave her confidence and showed her that teamwork is real, even if it takes patience and experience. It became a space where she felt inspired and motivated.

In the Aarhus Cultural Hub, participants also highlighted the experience of seeing parts of the museum they had never visited before – for example, during their overnight stay, if they wanted to go out and into the museum, they had to use the staff exit, giving them access to areas normally off-limits during regular opening hours. At the same time, this overnight experience was also unique for the other QH Cultural Hub partners, who had never seen these parts of ARoS before. This led to new relations and more intimate connections between the partners.

Another example can be found in the way each Cultural Hub carried out the so-called Vox Pops that were part of the CGJs. In essence, the Vox Pops conducted within the EPIC-WE project were interviews with CGJ participants, aimed at reflecting on their experiences during the event. However, the way these Vox Pops were implemented differed across the Cultural Hubs. According to the D3.2 report, these differences reflected the need for a situated approach adapted to each local context.

At the Aarhus Cultural Hub, phased reflection snapshots were used, with impromptu Vox Pops focusing first on participants' motivations and expectations, and later on their experiences and future perspectives. In Hilversum, the sessions were self-directed and took place in a dedicated recording studio. The Óbidos Cultural Hub, by contrast, did not conduct video interviews, but instead chose to collect input via surveys.

The reconfiguring of physical spaces also played an important role in some of these Vox Pops. Although NISV, where part of the Hilversum GCJs were held, has several different theatre and workshop spaces, finding a suitable, enclosed location for the Vox Pops required some out-of-the-box thinking – ultimately, the dressing room of one of the theatres proved to be the most fitting option. This demonstrates how a space can be reconfigured for an entirely different purpose than originally intended.

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

The Óbidos Cultural Hub likewise made creative use of the spaces connected to the CGJ. During their CGJs, instead of conducting interviews, they chose to carry out the Vox Pop in the form of a survey, administered during the bus trip to the CGJ. For the Óbidos Cultural Hub, this was the more practical option as it freed up the participants more during the CGJ process.

CGJ participants working through the night at the ARoS Art Museum in Aarhus CGJ#1

The need to creatively adapt to circumstances – such as using spaces for purposes other than originally intended – was not limited to working within the cultural buildings themselves, but also extended beyond them.

Originally, the idea behind the CGJs was that these interventions would take place in the ‘cultural home’ of each Cultural Hub – a museum in the case of Aarhus and Hilversum, and the entire town in the case of Óbidos. In the case of the two museums, it was decided to organise some parts of the CGJ elsewhere.

There were two reasons for this. Firstly, there was a practical reason: while the first CGJs were organised during weekends, when there was enough space in the museums to host such an event, later CGJs were held on weekdays due to collaborations with entire school classes as part of their curriculum (instead of through open recruitment). This meant that there were already many school visits taking place in the museum, leaving insufficient space to host the entire CGJ.

Secondly, there was a more conceptual reason for why the Cultural Hubs also wished to relocate certain parts of the CGJs to venues within the creative industries, for instance because these visits supported participants’ reflections on career development and professional opportunities. The Aarhus Cultural Hub therefore adopted a strategy in which

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

the CGJ participants began ‘in cultural heritage’ (at the ARoS Art Museum), then moved on to the ‘game-making’ phase (at Filmby Aarhus), before engaging in critical-creative thinking about how to connect these elements (at Aarhus University). Finally, they transformed game-making into an active form of culture-making (back at the ARoS Museum for the concluding EXPO). During the EXPO, all these experiences, cultural homes, and partners came together to meet and mingle – playing the games as expressions of through/for culture, talking with CGJ participants, and reflecting on the meaning and value of the games and their experiences.

In Hilversum, parts of the CGJ were also organised elsewhere – for example, at the schools involved in the collaboration, or at the premises of the creative industry partner Dropstuff. The latter proved particularly valuable, as the venue contained many examples of how heritage and games could be combined.

*Left: Participants enjoying one of the VR installations from CI partner DM during CGJ#4 in Hilversum.
Middle: A visit to the Mercado Biológico de Óbidos bookshop in Óbidos CGJ#1.
Right: On-site visit to the town of Óbidos in CGJ#3*

Although in the Óbidos Cultural Hub there was no shortage of space to host the CGJ, on-site visits were also included there. Participants greatly appreciated these visits, precisely because these took place in locations that already carry meaning for people – places where participants could draw inspiration from the culture embedded within them, such as libraries, museums, or heritage sites. For instance, CGJ#1 in Óbidos focused on the theme of literature, and students visited libraries, bookshops and a printing house to find inspiration for their games. In Aarhus too, participants expressed how much they valued the on-site visit and working within the museum, noting that it gave the experience a unique ‘sense of exclusivity’.

Reflection

Considering our learnings and insights from practicing the principle, a clear distinction can be made between the *real-world spaces* and the *real-life timeframes* of the QH Cultural Hubs and CGJs.

In terms of spaces, the Óbidos Cultural Hub did not encounter significant difficulties. Their CGJs took place in the historical town of Óbidos, hosted in facilities provided by the city hall who was able to provide a dedicated cultural heritage space called Praça da Criatividade

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

(Creativity Square), exclusively for the CGJ. This ‘cultural home’ was conveniently located near the town center and within easy reach of the participant’s residences.

Although the actual CGJs followed a 48-hour format, the overall duration of each CGJ in the Óbidos Cultural Hub stretched to nearly four days. This allowed the jams to begin with ‘pre-jam’ activities, including guided tours of the town and its historically significant cultural heritage sites. During these culture-walks or city tours, participants were able to hear from and ask questions to local specialists, who remained available throughout the jams and also attended the final CGJ game EXPO presentations. To coordinate these efforts, several preparatory visits to the cultural heritage site, i.e. the town of Óbidos which is part of the UNESCO Creative Cities Network as a city of literature, were organised with some of the stakeholders. Both participants and stakeholders alike were enthusiastic about spending several days in Óbidos, experiencing the town and its surroundings. The guided culture-walks in the town, together with the insights shared by local specialists, proved fundamental to the rich and fruitful outcomes of the CGJs.

The Aarhus and Hilversum Cultural Hubs, on the other hand, experienced that museums are not always geared towards this sort of activity or event, depending on how their internal organisational structures and processes are organised. This practical issue, combined with the substantive desire to introduce CGJ participants to the creative industry partners, meant that some CGJs were spread across multiple locations. This illustrates the impact that the Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs can have when they join forces.

The (un)familiarity with a venue is also significant. In CGJ#3 of the Hilversum Cultural Hub, which involved a minor class from the Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences, it was shown that a CGJ can work well when participants are largely in a familiar environment – in this case, their school. A mixed approach was also applied in the Óbidos Cultural Hub, where some pre-game jam activities were organised at the Joséfa d’Óbidos High School, while the game jam itself took place in Praça da Criatividade.

Nevertheless, there is a cross-hub consensus to host CGJs in the ‘cultural homes’ rather than in the ‘educational homes’ or ‘creative industry homes’, due to the fact that Youth Citizens are more motivated when the activity takes place in a new and unfamiliar environment, and because the cultural element is more tangible in the actual cultural homes.

Beyond the choice of venue, the organisation of time also emerged as a crucial factor. Reflecting on their third CGJ, the Óbidos Cultural Hub noted that when the ‘pre-game jam’ activities were held on the same day as the start of the jam itself, the outcome was less effective. Participants indicated that they preferred having a separate day to visit locations at a slower pace, followed by days or even weeks to reflect on what they had seen. They felt

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

that this gap was important for processing information, consolidating their understanding, and planning their games more deliberately, rather than rushing directly into development.

The Hilversum and Aarhus Cultural Hubs recognised a similar pattern. In their CGJ#3 and CGJ#4, they found it beneficial to give participants time to pause and absorb ideas before continuing with the jam. One approach was to begin the jam before the weekend and resume it afterwards. This allowed participants to recover from the intensity of the first days, let their ideas rest, and return with a fresh perspective. Another approach that was tested was even to spread the CGJ over several weeks in the form of a 'slow jam'. Although such an approach does not fit the 'traditional 48-hour format' of a game jam, it represents an important lesson learned.

In addition to the importance of spaces for organizing the CGJ, those spaces where the helix partners are located and meet each other are also significant. The reflection of one of the Hilversum Cultural Hub YAB members shows that the moments when the helix partners stepped out of their 'normal spaces' and met in other places were of great value. The presence of the Hilversum YAB during the boat trip organized as part of the consortium meeting in the Netherlands allowed this member to 'really see how many people were involved in the project and how connected we all are'. The same goes for an afternoon the Hilversum Cultural Hub spent in the studio space of one of the Cultural Hub members, where everyone came together to discuss ideas for the upcoming CGJ, which the YAB member describes as 'a very natural and open moment of reflection'.

These experiences show the value of creating both formal and informal 'cultural homes' where partners can exchange thoughts on equal footing. They highlight how collaboration grows strongest when people not only share tasks but also share real-world real-life practices and experiences.

Conclusion

The development of real-world, real-life QH Cultural Hubs and CGJs demonstrates that cultural innovation thrives when existing cultural spaces – such as museums, libraries, and heritage sites – are reconfigured as collaborative, shared 'cultural homes'. By embedding the QH Cultural Hubs and their partners, events, and practices within these meaningful cultural sites, partners and participants were not only inspired by their surroundings, but also empowered to transform these spaces through collective creativity. This approach reinforced the idea that cultural innovation is not (only) about creating new, dedicated spaces, but about reimagining how existing spaces can foster inclusive, participatory, and empowering practices and experiences that have a lasting impact on both participants, partners as well as the original cultural communities, practices, and sites themselves.

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

The experiences across the three QH Cultural Hubs showed that challenges, such as space limitations or conflicting needs, could lead to unexpected opportunities. Creative solutions, such as relocating activities or collaborating with new partners, highlighted the importance of hospitality, flexibility, and adaptability. At the same time, the timing and rhythm of activities proved to be just as crucial. Giving participants time to reflect and return with fresh perspectives created more meaningful outcomes than sticking rigidly to conventional formats.

Ultimately, the QH Cultural Hubs illustrate that cultural spaces must remain malleable, adaptable and deeply connected to their real-world contexts. By enacting cultural environments that are open, welcoming, flexible, and rooted in existing sites and communities, they can support transformative, participatory processes that empower both individuals and the cultural partners themselves as well as their surrounding contexts and communities.

PRINCIPLE

06

**Advance Empowered
Participation in Culture**

Principle 6: Advance Empowered Participation in Culture

QH Cultural Hubs must strive to foster inclusive, diverse, and equitable participation, ensuring that all helix partners feel they are **co-owners** of the QH Cultural Hub space and operations and equally invited to take part in the cultural innovation decisions, activities, practices and experiences happening there. Empowered participation extends beyond being listened to or consulted, **positioning every participant as a core partner** and indispensable member. QH Cultural Hubs must prioritize cultural innovation created through co-operation and co-creation and initiated from experiences of cultural imagination, agency, belonging, and respect. Success is measured by the QH Cultural Hub's ability to create a space for **empowered participation** among its partners and users, fostering new and potentially more empowering ways of engaging with and co-creating cultural heritage, spaces, experiences, and futures.

Explanation

The objective of this principle is to create a space for empowered participation, but what does empowered participation mean? And how can it be realised? In practice, QH Cultural Hubs must be organised as inclusive, diverse, and equitable communities where all helix partners see themselves not only as participants but as genuine co-owners of the Cultural Hub and its processes. This means that core decisions, activities, practices, and experiences of cultural innovation are shaped co-operatively (co-operative - as joint and democratic ownership), with every partner's voice recognised as indispensable to the whole. Empowered participation here goes beyond consultation or being heard, and beyond traditional user involvement or end-user roles; it entails shared responsibility, mutual respect, and collective agency in imagining, shaping, and stimulating cultural innovation and life across diverse partners and backgrounds. By prioritising *co-operation*, *collaboration* and *co-creation* grounded in concrete practices and experiences of belonging, imagination, and respect, QH Cultural Hubs can develop a sense of collectively empowered ownership that transforms cultural innovation into living co-operative, collaborative, and co-created practices.

A sense of co-ownership is essential for empowerment to emerge, yet it must be accompanied by a fair understanding of both individual, partner, and sector capacity. Not everyone can contribute equally in terms of workload – even when the motivation is there – simply because capacity varies. At the outset of a collaboration, it is therefore crucial for QH Cultural Hubs to share openly what their capacity is and what a realistic contribution looks like for them. This approach ensures that each individual, partner, and sector is not merely someone working toward an end goal, but a genuine co-owner of the project – an indispensable part of a collective endeavour.

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

Experience

The principle of ‘empowered participation’ has recurred in various ways throughout the course of the project.

Firstly, this entire report so far demonstrates that a key objective was to foster inclusive, diverse, and equitable participation through the continuous emphasis on creating dialogic communities, where every voice is heard and valued in order to genuinely reconfigure and innovate the Cultural Hub as a co-owned and co-shaped cultural heritage innovation community. While the focus was on ensuring that every voice was heard, particular importance was placed on amplifying the voice of the Youth Citizen. We did this through the establishment of the Youth Advisory Board (YAB) and the integration of the YAB into the project’s expert Advisory Board. Beyond this, we were also open to other ways of involving and empowering youth in various ways.

For example, in a different role outside of the project, a Hilversum Cultural Hub partner taught students within his organisation and invited those students to assist with a specific task within our project. An example of this can be seen in the photo below, which shows a lecturer of AUAS on the right, with two of his students on his left helping to document the presentations during CGJ#4. This example demonstrates how young people are empowered by being taught a new skill by someone who already has experience in it – not with the aim of replacing this person, but to show young people what they are capable of.

Youth Citizens helping out during Hilversum CGJ#4

Secondly, ‘empowered participation’ emerged in the way the CGJs were designed. For example, the Cultural Hubs experimented with the balance between the level of openness and the degree of guided tasks given to CGJ participants. In Hilversum CGJ#1, for instance,

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

participant feedback indicated that they felt there were sometimes 'too many brainstorming methods', which reduced the time available for actually developing their game.

In Aarhus CGJ#3, for example, this balance was successfully achieved, with students demonstrating a high level of agency throughout the week, independently selecting and interpreting cultural heritage themes and values. They were able to do so thanks to the tailored CGJ kit, which ensured that scaffolding was available when needed. Within the concept of empowered participation, it also became clear that age differences played a role. In Óbidos CGJ#3, students from Lusófona University, for example, were confident and self-directed, while high school participants required more structured encouragement. This shows that the method used to foster empowered participation can vary according to age group and target audience.

Thirdly, the game prototypes that were created, and the way in which they were developed, are themselves a prime example of empowered participation. This manifests in two ways. Firstly, the games developed during the CGJs are representative of the collective work of all stakeholders, reflecting workshops, resources, feedback, and other forms of co-creation involving every member of the quadruple helix. Partners as facilitators of the CGJ played an active role throughout the participants' game-making process, providing materials, inspiration and guidance that were crucial for embedding cultural heritage themes. To ensure that every helix member could be heard and contribute, each of the Óbidos CGJs, for example, included two pitching sessions where groups presented their ideas to all participants and helix partners, gathering valuable feedback. In the first pitching moment initial ideas were shared, while in the second session feedback could be provided to the more developed ideas. These structured dialogic practices of exchange and integration – combined with the spontaneous interactions that naturally unfolded during these practices and events – ensured that everyone was involved, informed, and connected to the work and practices of others.

Secondly, part of the project also involves further development of some game prototypes into matured games. For each Cultural Hub, it was agreed that two game prototypes would be developed further. In the Óbidos Cultural Hub, however, they decided to develop not two but four prototypes into matured games, as there were so many strong prototypes. Rather than having this work carried out entirely by the creative partner of the QH Cultural Hub, the original CGJ participants whose prototypes were selected for further development are closely involved in the process. They are involved in all decision-making, they are the ones documenting and implementing changes and improvements to the games, and they are also creating art and audio assets. In addition to being an incredibly valuable experience for these Youth Citizens and other helix partners, the young people are also compensated for their work (not as full-time employees, but at least with some remuneration for the time and effort they contribute).

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

One of the two selected games from the Aarhus Cultural Hub – the game *Metamorphosis* – was also developed in close collaboration between the four young people who created the prototype and the game studio Mothworks, which is a strong testament to the empowering and innovative potential of combining youth voices, cultural heritage, and European values with game design.

Reflection

The notion of ‘empowered participation’ driving this principle was embedded at every stage of the project. It fostered a democratic approach to tasks and decision-making, where each partner’s input and contribution was considered fundamental. This was not because participation was formally required, but because partners genuinely valued one another’s expertise and were eager to learn from and build upon it. At the same time, both the Óbidos and Hilversum Cultural Hubs noted that this absence of hierarchy occasionally led to unclear communication and a lack of clarity about overall project direction, resulting in uncertainties that needed to be addressed.

Expectations around time and task-sharing proved to be a crucial factor in this respect. The Hilversum Cultural Hub in particular experienced challenges concerning equity of capacity. Sector and partner inclusion and diversity are important, yet it is not always feasible in terms of capacity. Simply allocating more hours cannot overcome the structural limits of a small cultural heritage team or a game company organisation. For such partners, balancing effort and attendance at numerous ‘in the middle’ meetings with their other responsibilities was especially difficult.

An important development during the project was the creation of the Youth Advisory Board – something not originally part of the project plan, but recognised along the way as an essential addition to make young people true partners and empowered participants in the QH Cultural Hub. The board carried significant responsibility: it played a central role in redesigning materials and frameworks for the CGJs, contributed actively to communication and dissemination, and ensured that civic perspectives, relevant cultural heritage themes, and youth voices were consistently represented within the Cultural Hub, its sectors, and the broader project.

A good example of the way the YAB contributed to dissemination is the European Youth Event (EYE) organized by the European Parliament, where EPIC-WE was present in June 2025. The EYE, where we participated to discuss the empowerment of young people, was in itself a strong example of how the young people from our YABs were *core partners and indispensable members* of the quadruple helix. This is clearly illustrated in the reflections of two of the YAB members who presented in the event in Strasbourg.

One of them mentioned that it was ‘extremely inspiring to see the different partners work

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

together and to be invited to participate on equal footing’. The event preparation itself was, for her, an example of truly being heard and considered a full member of the team – something that, for instance, had not always been the case during the preparation of the CGJs. One of the other YAB members presenting in the event, pointed out that the event was to her a moment where everyone shared the same goals, ideas, and inspiration, and even a similar sense of humour, which created a strong feeling of collaboration.

One of EPIC-WE's panel discussions during the EYE in Strasbourg, June 2025

What is further interesting is that both YAB members indicated that the EYE 2025 event helped them better understand what the project was really about. Large European research projects like EPIC-WE can be quite complex and difficult to grasp for young people encountering them for the first time. They mentioned that during meetings and the EYE event they finally understood the core of the project. The opportunity to meet participants from other Cultural Hubs gave them a broader understanding of the project as a whole – its goals and mission – and allowed them to connect with YAB members from other Cultural Hubs and countries.

The EYE also demonstrated that empowerment was not only an important topic within the Cultural Hubs but also externally – it was a key theme we aimed to promote as much as possible, for instance through various dissemination activities. During the EYE, the speakers present also applied the concept of empowered participation by making their panel interactive. They did this through a Mentimeter, allowing participants – young people aged 16 to 30 and European policymakers – to share their opinions on various questions, such as:

“ [Where do you see the most transformative potential and value for youth empowerment and partnerships?](#) ”

- Question asked to participants at the EYE panel

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

Participating in this event as a true QH helix ecosystem was therefore successful in two respects: first, we were able not only to *talk about* youth empowerment, but also to *engage in conversation with young people themselves*, with our YAB taking the centre stage at the EYE 2025 (and similar events). The fact that our YAB was present in the European Parliament led to a second success, beautifully expressed in the words of one of our YAB members:

“ Being in the building where big political decisions are made, made me realize how close the project is to European values. (...) for me it was similar to what the Cultural Game Jams did: they made me change inside and gave me more confidence. It was a very special experience that connected politics, culture, and education in one ”

- YAB member Hilversum Cultural Hub

Conclusion

Welcoming and advancing empowered participation across sectors, partners, and youth citizens has been central to both QH Cultural Hubs and their CGJs. The project demonstrates that creating spaces where every voice is welcomed and recognised as indispensable requires more than ‘being consulted’ – it requires a feeling of genuine co-ownership, shared responsibility, and collective agency. This dynamic exchange, in which hierarchies, roles, and responsibilities shifted among project partners and within the QH Cultural Hubs, allowed diverse perspectives, experiences, and skills to emerge and be amplified. As the Portuguese creative industries partner Battlesheep reflected: ‘Each stakeholder was seen not only as an equal, but as a fundamental piece of the puzzle.’ By prioritising co-creation grounded in cultural belonging, imagination, and respect, the Cultural Hubs fostered environments where participation became transformative, meaningful, and empowering for all involved and in diverse ways.

At the same time, inviting for empowered participation came with its own challenges, particularly in balancing differing capacities, managing expectations, and working within flexible, non-hierarchical structures. These tensions underscored the importance of clear communication, transparency, negotiation, and adaptability to maintain equitable collaboration. A key achievement was the integration of youth voices through the Youth Advisory Board, which not only enriched the Cultural Hubs and CGJs but also reshaped decision-making, broadened perspectives, and strengthened co-creative practices. Ultimately, empowered participation in the QH Cultural Hubs is not a static goal but an ongoing, evolving practice – one that builds resilience, fosters belonging, and nurtures collective imagination, ensuring these spaces remain inclusive, innovative, and transformative for the future.

Final Conclusion

Final conclusion

The EPIC-WE project, through the design, implementation, and evaluation of the Quadruple Helix (QH) Cultural Hubs and their Cultural Game Jams (CGJs), has demonstrated how cultural research, innovation, and transformation can emerge from collaborative, cross-sector, and participatory ecosystems that are both real-world and empowering. Over the course of the project, the QH Cultural Hubs have not only tested and refined six key principles for collaborative cultural innovation but also enacted them as living practices. These principles show that genuine cultural innovation is a dynamic, evolving process rooted in reciprocity, co-ownership, and mutual transformation.

At its core, the QH Ecosystem and Living Lab approach applied in the EPIC-WE project invited Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs), Creative Industries (CIs), and Youth Citizens to step outside their traditional roles and meet each other 'in the middle. This meeting space – conceptual, social, and physical – is where learning, unlearning, and innovation take place. Rather than operating as separate sectors contributing expertise in parallel from their own silos or homes, the partners engage in the middle through processes of co-creation in which vocabularies, knowledges, methods, skills, and values enrich each other, circulate freely, and continually shape and reshape the collective practice. The result is a unique and deeply participatory QH Cultural Hub model of cultural innovation in which friction, negotiation, and exchange become productive forces.

Rethinking participation: from inclusion to co-ownership

The first and sixth principles – *Democratizing cultural innovation* and *Advancing empowered participation in culture* – have been central to how the QH Cultural Hubs have been developed and evolved during the project. Both principles emphasize that meaningful and empowering participation cannot be reduced to consultation or token involvement; it must instead be grounded in shared agency, responsibility, mutual trust, and co-ownership. Across all QH Cultural Hubs, Youth Citizens, Cultural Heritage Institutions, Creative Industries and Higher Education Institutions were positioned not as passive participants but as equal active partners and indispensable actors in the cultural innovation process.

This shift was for the youth made tangible through the creation of Youth Advisory Boards (YABs), which became key drivers of the project's overall participatory approach. The YABs co-designed CGJ events, contributed to research and dissemination, and represented the youth perspective in everyday practices and strategic decision-making. Their involvement ensured that the values of empowerment, belonging, agency, and imagination remained central to the QH Cultural Hubs' activities. Through their work – both within their local QH Cultural Hubs and in local and glocal events such as the European Youth Event (EYE) – the YABs embodied the project's ambition to transform involvement into empowered participation.

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

However, the project also revealed that empowerment is not a static achievement but an ongoing, negotiated process. The diversity of partners meant that capacities, expectations, and resources were unevenly distributed, and maintaining equitable participation required constant communication and flexibility. Balancing voluntary contributions from youth with professional obligations from partners demanded careful consideration and negotiation. Yet it was precisely this ongoing negotiation that allowed the project to model what authentic cross-sector co-creation looks like in practice: a continuous balancing of structure and openness, direction and dialogue.

Transformative partnerships and “meeting in the middle”

The principles of *Forming equal and transformative partnerships* and *Instituting meetings in the middle* shaped the everyday working culture of the QH Cultural Hubs. These principles foregrounded the need for openness, empathy, and a willingness to be transformed and learn from others’ ways of thinking and doing. In practice, this meant dismantling hierarchical and taken-for-granted assumptions and inviting every partner to influence not just the outcomes, but also the process of collaboration itself.

Across the QH Cultural Hubs, friction and difference were not viewed as setbacks but as generative forces. Differing institutional rhythms, professional vocabularies, and methods and understandings of research and creativity often led to challenging discussions – but these were precisely the moments when partners were compelled to rethink their positions and discover new possibilities. In some QH Cultural Hubs this openness resulted in an inspiring blurring of roles: researchers engaged in innovation and game-making, creative industry partners contributed to research and reflective practices, and cultural heritage professionals learned new approaches to design and innovation.

This cross-sector collaboration showed that ‘meeting in the middle’ is not a one-time achievement, but a continuous process of translation, engagement, and re-alignment. It requires partners to make themselves vulnerable and open to change, to suspend certainty, step into others’ domains, and allow their own practices to be transformed in the encounter. The result is a genuinely collective form of empowered innovation: one that no single sector could achieve alone.

Co-creation for public good(s)

The fourth principle – *Practising co-creative cultural innovation and transformation for public good(s)* – highlighted the project’s commitment to ensuring that innovation serves culture and society as a whole. The QH Cultural Hubs demonstrated that cultural research and innovation can and should generate both *public goods* (tangible, freely accessible resources such as open websites, toolkits, and prototypes) and *public good* (the collective value created through participation, learning, and shared creativity).

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

Throughout the project, this commitment took shape in multiple ways. The open EPIC-WE resource website made available the prototypes, methods, models, and materials developed during the project and its CGJs, allowing others to replicate or adapt them. At the same time, the frameworks, formats, relationships and products created across the QH Cultural Hubs – characterised by openness, reciprocity, and inclusion – constituted forms of public good in themselves.

Yet sustaining this focus on public good(s) was not without challenges. The fast-paced nature of the project and its CGJs, the diversity of participant motivations, and the differing notions of what counts as a “useful” outcome required ongoing negotiation. The experiences across Cultural Hubs showed that for co-created outputs to become genuine public goods, their relevance must be visible and meaningful to all contributors from the very beginning. This insight underlines a broader lesson: that the process of co-creation is itself a public good, even when its tangible outputs remain incomplete.

Real-world, real-life Cultural Hubs: space, time, and transformation

The fifth principle – *Developing real-world, real-life QH Cultural Hubs* – situated research and innovation within existing cultural ecosystems rather than creating new, detached innovation spaces. By reconfiguring museums and heritage sites as collaborative “cultural homes,” the QH Cultural Hubs transformed familiar places into participatory innovation environments where learning and creativity could flourish.

This spatial reconfiguration was not only symbolic but deeply experiential. Overnight stays in museums, on-site workshops in heritage sites, and creative use of unexpected spaces – such as a theatre dressing room for interviews – allowed participants to encounter culture in new and inspiring ways. Working within these meaningful, real-world real-life contexts deepened participants’ sense of connection to cultural heritage and to each other.

Equally important was the dimension of time and rhythm. The project found that slowing down the traditional 48-hour game jam format – creating pauses for cultural reflection, absorption, and return – resulted in richer and more meaningful outcomes. The “slow jam” approach fostered deeper cultural engagement and more thoughtful designs and developments, showing that cultural innovation benefits from cycles of intensity and reflection rather than constant acceleration.

A living laboratory for cultural innovation

Taken together, the six principles reveal that QH Cultural Hubs function as cultural ecosystems and living labs where co-creation, experimentation, and transformation intersect. They are not static frameworks or isolated experiments, but dynamic living systems and sites embedded in real communities and cultural environments.

D4.2 Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation

Across the QH Cultural Hubs, the iterative application of these principles resulted in new practices of democratic and participatory culture-making. By working collaboratively across disciplines, sectors, and even generations, the Cultural Hubs generated environments where every voice was valued, every difference was framed as productive, and every space as open to be reimaged.

Ultimately, the EPIC-WE project has shown that cultural research and innovation is not simply about producing new artefacts, tools, or methods, but about cultivating and deepening cross-sector relationships, trust, collaboration, and shared agency. It is about creating conditions in which diverse partners – youth, researchers, creative professionals, and cultural heritage institutions – can imagine and act together.

In doing so, the QH Cultural Hubs have demonstrated that genuine cultural innovation emerges from meeting in the middle, inviting for empowered participation, and being open to reciprocal transformation: a willingness to be transformed by others, to meet in the middle, and to co-create value, meaning, and public good(s) in ways that enrich both the cultural sector and society at large.

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EPIC-WE

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